

Changing Social Status of Untouchable Castes In India: A Sociological Study

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Abstract

The identity of Untouchable is a very complicated person. It encompasses a lengthy history of fight against prejudice, religious discourse, and, more recently, the socio-economic framework. The enigmatic personality is not just connected to the denial of rights; it is also connected to the need for dignity and, in certain circumstances, the yearning for revolution. Because of this, the efforts of the Dalits have not just centred on concerns like as untouchability, the repetition of atrocities, minimum wages, land rights, employment, and political representation; rather, these battles have also centred on questions of identity, self-respect, and dignity. The Indian Constitution's Articles 330 and 332 set aside a total of 79 seats in the Lok Sabha and 557 seats in the Vidhan Sabha for members of the Scheduled caste, however the Vidhan Sabha only has 315 seats reserved for them. Nevertheless, it is clear that those who were elected come from the more educated and affluent segment of the population, while those who have a more radical stance are not allowed to hold party representation. However, such options are still restricted within the context of the current system. Many members of the Legislative Assembly and Parliament find that the governing class has co-opted them or that they are unable to use their political authority to bring about socio-economic change. Because of this, the implementation of political democracy or economic equality has been shown to be challenging.

Keywords: Untouchable, Castism, Dignity, Indian Constitution, etc

Introduction

The practise of untouchability in India is a result of the caste system. It has occasionally been called the "horrific plague of the caste system." Mahatma Gandhi is cited as stating, "I believe untouchability to be the greatest humiliation of the Hindu faith," in the book *Young India*. In Indian civilization, there are examples of how individuals might become unclean not just by touching untouchables but simply by visiting them or by their shadow. This demonstrates how interacting with untouchables can cause humans to become impure for a number of different reasons. Unfortunately, this phrase's roots may be found in the wonderful country of India, and it is this country that makes this distinction between humans.

Regarding their readiness to fight for essential human rights and ideas like justice, equality, liberty, and other similar ideas, untouchables in general as well as Dalits specifically have undergone a tremendous change. India, a rising light and an important player on the global scene, cannot continue to tolerate the injustice and tyranny occurring within its borders. The Dalit position has historically been closely linked in India's ancient Hindu society to jobs that are viewed as ritually unclean, such as sweeping, selling meat, working with leather, hunting and pounding drums, slaughtering, or removing trash and animal corpse waste. Other examples of these occupations include clearing garbage from animal carcasses. They were made to perform physical labor, cleaning sewers, latrines, and public spaces. Voting rights were

denied to untouchables. Participating in these behaviours was thought to contaminate the person, and it was also thought that this contamination was contagious. Because of this, Dalits have always faced prejudice and been denied equal access to Hindu society. For instance, they were prohibited from entering a temple, attending a school, or even getting drinking water from a well. They were also required to live outside the community. Sometimes, stricter safety precautions are implemented when there is a chance that untouchables and higher Hindus might come into contact accidentally.

Untouchables in certain rural areas continue to face prejudice in the private realm, including when it comes to basic necessities like getting access to restaurants, schools, temples, and water sources. This is particularly common when discussing issues of religious belief. The caste system has historically provided the social and economic foundation upon which people's lives are structured in Indian society. Caste is a social structure in which people are divided at birth into hierarchies of unequal social groups called castes. Within these castes, people are given certain fundamental rights and responsibilities according to their birth order, and caste cannot be changed. Untouchables are excluded from the Brahma, Kshatriya, Vaishya, and Shudra lineages because they are viewed as "outcasts." Dalits are occasionally seen with contempt as being inferior, unclean, and disgusting because of where they were born and the type of job they often undertake. As a result, individuals encounter a wide range of forms

of bigotry, as well as violence and social exclusion. Untouchables take advantage of Dalits, according to the results of this study. Sanskrit may be the source of the words "ground," "suppressed," "crushed," or "broken to pieces," which all imply one of the following: "ground," "suppressed," "crushed," or "broken to pieces." Mahatma Jyotiba Rao Phule was the first person to utilise this phrase in the eighteenth century. He did so in reference to the discrimination that Hindus who were twice born were subjected to, including the once-called "Untouchable" castes. However, in today's society, many Dalit people use this phrase to distance themselves from the more derogatory associations associated with their caste name or even the term "untouchable." The modern interpretation of the term "Dalit" centres on the idea that, despite having been destroyed by tyranny as a people, they have survived and even thrived as a consequence of finding meaning in the struggle for human dignity in which they have spent their whole lives.

Mahatma Gandhi coined the term "Harijans," which means "children of God" in its exact translation. Dr. B.R. Ambedkar advised referring to this population as "protestant Hindus" or "non-conformists." The Simon Commission advised the government to use the term "scheduled castes," which it eventually did. Additionally, the official vocabulary used in papers released by the Indian government to refer to those who were historically thought of as "untouchables" includes words that are often associated with scheduled castes (SC). The National Commission for Scheduled Castes, however, declared the term "Dalit" "unconstitutional" and asked state governments to stop using it in 2008 after realising that it was frequently used interchangeably with the term "Scheduled Castes." The Chhattisgarh state administration stopped using the term "Dalit" in any official capacity after the judgment.

Untouchables In Modern India

Many social, religious, and political organisations in India rose to prominence throughout the 20th century in opposition to the caste system and in support of the rights to human dignity of the Dalit people. Dr. B.R. Ambedkar was instrumental in the process that resulted in the approval of India's constitution in 1950 after the nation declared its independence in 1947. He oversaw the group's break from the caste system's norms and traditions in favour of justice, equality, liberty, and fraternity as head of the constitutional writing committee.

As a result, the constitution ensures that all Indian people have access to the same basic human rights, regardless of caste, creed, gender, or ethnicity. Unfortunately, the implementation and

enforcement of these concepts have so far failed miserably. The agrarian conflicts, social reform movements, and independence movements that erupted in India in the second half of the 19th century and the first decades of the 20th century posed a threat to the established order that was founded on custom and introduced concepts of challenge and protest rather than acceptance and submission. The battles caused many leaders to emerge from the lowest socioeconomic classes. Because of agitations and movements that were the root of many of these disputes, the authorities were forced to start many of the measures that were later included into welfare plans for the impoverished and underprivileged areas. A turning event in the history of the country was the appointment of a commissioner for the interests and welfare of scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. It was the commissioner's job to protect these individuals' interests.

A further step was taken to eliminate social impairments with the passage of the Untouchability Offense Act, also known as Act No. XXII of 1955. Social infirmities are regarded as offences that are punishable under this law. The "untouchability" clause was deleted from the Indian constitution in 1950, despite the fact that the practise of "untouchability," the imposition of social limitations on people because of their birth in a specific caste, is still very much present in rural India. However, the "untouchability" practise itself is still in use today. In rural India, it is still against the law for "untouchables" to visit the same temples, drink from the same wells, or eat from the same pots. Children from Dalit families regularly encounter racism at school. Many Dalits still live in situations of utter deprivation and are excluded from better employment and educational opportunities. The great majority of those who are compelled into service as a way of paying off debts to higher caste members are children from Dalit homes. The national Dalit Human Rights Campaign's convener is presently Prof. Vimal Thorat. A coalition of civil society organisations and Dalit activists founded this campaign in 1998 with the intention of addressing the human rights issues and development concerns of Dalits as well as bolstering the movement for the elimination of customs like untouchability, discrimination, and violence against Dalits. The scheduled castes in India have a total population of 167.2 million people. The majority of the country's governments now refer to these communities, which were traditionally regarded as untouchable, as Dalits (census 2001). In addition, there are at least 42 million Dalits who are Sikhs, Muslims, and Christians. These individuals are vulnerable to

discrimination as well as varied and distinct forms of retaliatory violence.

Untouchability Preventions In Indian Constitution

This research aims to analyse the social change that has occurred among India's untouchable population. For the sake of this study, the Untouchables are considered schedule castes in India. They are dispersed throughout the whole country, which has a higher concentration of untouchables than any other community. We chose gaining equal human rights and altering social and economic status as our research's objectives. Such a study might be very helpful in advancing our understanding of the subject.

Objectives

1. To find out whether the changing to find out the level of change social & economic status among untouchable peoples in India.
2. To identify responsible factors for the improvement of the status, of Untouchables.

Dalits Followers Invarious Religion

According to the Sachar Committee's 2006 report, Hinduism is not the only religion practised by India's scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. According to the NSSO's sixty-one-round survey, there are 31.9 percent Buddhists, 21 percent Sikhs, 56 percent Christians, and 38 percent Hindus among the population. Each belongs to one of the scheduled castes recognised by the Indian Constitution.

Examples of Dalit priests in history include Chokha Mela, who was born from the Chamar caste and was India's first Dalit, known as Saint Ravidas, in the 14th century. He came from a family of cobblers. Saint Shri Ramanand Raya welcomed members of all castes, including untouchables, into his flock in the fifteenth century. The majority of these saints were caste-free throughout the mediaeval era. Popular Hindu mythology centres on Nandanar, a low-caste devotee who was rejected by the priests but embraced by God. Many Dalits continue to argue about whether they are Hindu or non-Hindu due to their separation from the rest of Hindu society.

Movement Related To Untouchables

The movement led by Dr. B.R. Ambedkar may be split into two categories. The first is the social reformative movement, which advocates for Dalit advancement and imposes restrictions on ritualistic behaviour and other religious practises as well as the use of narcotics, alcohol, and other non-vegetarian foods. The Alternative Movement, which suggests that all Dalits convert to Buddhism, comes

in second. A 16-year Dalit effort to rename Marathwada University as Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University included the Namantar movement. Vasant Dada Patil, the chief minister of Maharashtra, told the Dalit panthers in 1977 that a renaming would take place; in July 1978, the Maharashtra legislature issued a resolution to that effect. Both the BSP's Manyawar Kashi Ram and the former chief minister of Uttar Pradesh, Miss Mayawati, are members of the scheduled caste movement in that state.

Prevention Atrocities Act And Untouchability

The Prevention of Atrocities Act is the Indian government's covert admission that systemic and accidental violence define caste relations. The Indian government introduced the Prevention of Atrocities Act in 1989, which defined certain offences against scheduled castes as "atrocities" and included countermeasures, including methods and penalties.

The Act's main goal was to reduce and criminalise violence against Dalits. The atrocities were defined as both specific instances of pain and humiliation, such as the forced eating of poisonous chemicals, and the systematic violence that Dalits continue to experience, particularly in rural India. Forced labour, denial of access to temples, water, and other public utilities, and sexual assault of Dalit women are only a few examples of this systematic brutality. Second, to hear cases filed under the Prevention of Atrocities Act, special courts were established. Third, the Act mandated the appointment of qualified officials to oversee and uphold peace and order in states with high rates of violence.

Dalits now have a voice thanks to the Prevention of Atrocities Act, but just two states have special courts that are legally distinct from one another. In reality, the act's implementation has been a near-total failure. Police have consistently shown a reluctance to report offences in accordance with the legislation.

Untouchables Status In Contemporary India

For the Dalits, who include the scheduled castes and scheduled tribes, to attain upward social mobility, the Indian constitution has created the appropriate specific provisions; nevertheless, these privileges are only granted to those Dalits who continue to practise Hinduism. To address and put an end to historical injustices, the Dalits who have converted to other religions are calling for the extension of the statutory benefits to them as well. Since the establishment of the Indian constitution, the government apparatus in India has made a concerted effort to enhance the social and economic conditions of untouchables via various programmes. To help the Dalits occupy their proper position in

society, several services have been made available to them. Through the five-year plans, the government has established goals for the betterment of the social standing of scheduled caste women in general and untouchables in particular. As a result, the status of untouchable men and women has shifted, and many sociocultural, political, religious, and professional spheres have seen a discernible improvement. Another significant political problem is the government's affirmative action policies, which include quotas for Dalits in government employment and college and university admissions. The state governments choose around 15% of the seats at the federal and state levels. a move aimed at ensuring that Dalits would have a proportionate political voice, as demanded by Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, Kashi Ram, and other Dalit activists. K.R. Narayanan was chosen to lead India as president in 1977.

2007 saw the election of Mayawati as Uttar Pradesh's chief minister. The Dalit community is home to both of these individuals. The state legislature reserves 557 seats for scheduled castes and 315 seats for scheduled tribes, and 79 seats in the Indian parliament are set aside for scheduled castes and 40 seats for scheduled tribes.

Conclusion

In order to raise creative forces to a level of educational, social, and economic growth similar to that of higher castes, the established order throws obstacles in their path that must be found and removed throughout history. Dalit writing was given fresh life in the modern era by leaders of the community like Mahatma Phule, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, Kashi Ram, and others. Although Dalits today are successful in business, politics, education, and higher administrative positions, the number of Dalits who are still subject to the practise of untouchability is far fewer than it was in the past. It is forbidden to practise untouchability in any way under Article 17 of the Indian Constitution. Additionally, it makes it illegal to enforce any kind of handicap that could have developed as a result, and this illegal activity has legal repercussions. The goal of doing this was to advance social equality. Article 15, along with articles 16, 19, 23, 25, and 29, is likewise closely related to Article 17 in that it aims to eliminate various forms of untouchability.

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